

Temperature dependent dielectric relaxation study of triol-water mixtures using picosecond time domain technique

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Abstract : Picosecond time domain reflectometry method has been used in the frequency range of 10 MHz to 20 MHz to determine dielectric properties of aqueous solutions of triol in temperature range of 15 to 35 °C. The excess permittivity, Kirkwood correlation factor and Bruggeman factor of triol-water system have also been determined. A hydrogen bonded theory is applied to compute correlation terms for the mixtures. A hydrogen bonded model gives good qualitative account of the dielectric constant for triol-water mixture.

Keywords : Dielectric relaxation, TDR, glycerol, glass transition.

The dielectric properties of triols have attracted the attention of many workers¹. Hydrogen-bonded glycerol [C₃H₅(OH)₃] can easily super cooled and has been extensively investigated to test theories of the glass transition¹. The glass transition of glycerol is 185 K and it plays an important role in life and chemical sciences. The glassy transition of glycerol and large group of polymers is considered as a non-crystalline solid. The importance of such glassy materials in modern life, from physical point of view, in understanding this state of matter is poor and transition from liquid to glassy state is commonly considered as one of the great unsolved problem of condensed matter physics²⁻⁴.

Temperature dependent studies of glycerol has been extensively carried out using various experimental and theoretical methods^{5,6}. The hydroxyl groups can act as a proton donor as well as acceptor, which results in well known association in liquid glycerol via hydrogen bonds. The complex dielectric permittivity for glycerol has been determined in the different frequencies using microwave technique^{6,7}. Davidson and Cole have introduced the phenomenological Cole-Davidson model to fit dielectric data on glycerol⁸. Schonhals *et al.*⁹ have used dielectric data of glycerol for the prediction of mode-coupling theory. Lunkenheimer¹ has performed the dielectric spectroscopy experiment of super cooled glycerol for frequencies 3 GHz ≤ ν ≤ 40 GHz and temperature range 100 K < T < 500 K and concluded that in glycerol at high frequencies the density fluctuation are dominated by local vibration excitations which are fully decoupled from the dipolar reorientations.

Lunkenheimer⁶ also performed the dielectric measurement up to 370 GHz on glycerol for temperature 250 and 330 K and high frequencies dielectric loss has been investigated, which is compared to theoretical concepts that predict fast relaxation processes.

The dipolar properties of water molecules affect the interaction between water and glycerol molecules that dissolve in water. Dielectric relaxation processes is the Debye⁷, Davidson type⁸ and the molecular network formed by hydrogen bonding with neighbouring glycerol molecules and it also exhibits many eccentric properties due to its three dimensional hydrogen bond network or hydrogen bonded complexes^{7,9}.

The objective of this work is to report the molecular interactions in water-glycerol mixtures by calculating the Kirkwood correlation factor using hydrogen bonded Luzar model. The temperature dependence Bruggeman factor and excess parameters for water-glycerol system are also determined.

Experimental

Materials : Glycerol was used S.d. fine-Chem Limited, whereas water was used after double distillation and deionization. The solutions were prepared by mixing the glycerol and water in volume.

Apparatus and measurements : The Hewlett Packard 54750A sampling oscilloscope along with the HP 54754A plug in unit has been used for the TDR set up¹⁰. A 200 mV

step pulse with 40 ps rise time and 250 MHz repetition rate passes through coaxial 50 Ω line. The sample was placed in a SMA cell of 3.5 mm outer diameter and 1.35 mm effective pin length and its temperature was kept constant at 15, 25, 35 °C in a temperature stabilizer, which utilizes water at fixed temperature from a circulating bath. Sampling oscilloscope monitored the reflected pulse with and without sample. The reflected pulses were digitized with 1024 sampling points in the time window of 5 ns. The recorded reflected pulses through the sample $R_s(t)$ was compared with the reflected pulse without sample $R_r(t)$. The complex permittivity spectra was obtained and are described in earlier publication¹⁰.

Results and discussion

Dielectric constant and relaxation time : The complex permittivity is given as $\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon'(\omega) - j\epsilon''(\omega)$ where, $\epsilon'(\omega)$ is real component known as dielectric dispersion and $\epsilon''(\omega)$ is imaginary component known as dielectric loss, is shown in Figs. 1(a,b). It is observed from dispersion plot that the value of ϵ' decreases with increase in temperature. Result of ϵ'' clearly indicates that the dielectric loss approaches maximum in the frequency range 2 to 3 GHz. The magnitude of dielectric loss (ϵ''_{max}) decreases with increase in temperature.

To evaluate various dielectric relaxation parameters such as static dielectric constant (ϵ_0), relaxation time (τ) and distribution parameters (α and β) the complex permittivity [$\epsilon^*(\omega)$] data were fitted by the non-linear least squares method to the Havriliak-Negami expression¹¹,

$$\epsilon^*(\omega) = \epsilon_\infty + \frac{(\epsilon_0 - \epsilon_\infty)}{[1 + (j\omega\tau)^{1-\alpha}]^\beta} \quad (1)$$

with ϵ_0 , ϵ_∞ , τ , α and β are the fitting parameters. The equation includes the Cole-Cole ($\beta = 1$), Davidson-Cole ($\alpha = 0$) and Debye ($\alpha = 0$, $\beta = 1$) relaxation model. The values of the errors are estimated by assuming 2% errors in the values of (ϵ') and (ϵ'') from the goodness of fit of the data with eq. (1).

Fig. 1a. Variation of dielectric constant (ϵ') for glycerol at different temperatures.

The values of static permittivity (ϵ_0) and relaxation time (τ) at different temperatures and concentration of glycerol in water are shown in Fig. 2. It can be seen from Fig. 2 that the static dielectric constant decreases, whereas relaxation time increases as the concentration of glycerol in water increases.

Fig. 1b. Variation of dielectric loss (ϵ'') for glycerol at different temperatures.

Fig. 2a. Static dielectric constant vs volume fraction of water at different temperatures

Fig. 2b. Relaxation time (ps) vs volume fraction of water at different temperatures.

Kirkwood correlation factor :

To understand the significance of association effect due to the hydrogen bonding, it is useful to compute the values of the Kirkwood correlation factor g in the system using the following expression⁷,

$$\sum_{i=1,2} \frac{4\pi N \mu_i \rho_i g_i}{9kTM_i} = \frac{(\epsilon_{0i} - \epsilon_{\infty i})(2\epsilon_{0i} + \epsilon_{\infty i})}{\epsilon_{0i}(\epsilon_{\infty i} + 2)^2} \quad (2)$$

$i = 1$ and 2 represents water and glycerol respectively, μ is dipole moment in gas phase; M_i is molecular weight, ρ_i is density, k Boltzman's constant, N Avogadro's number, ϵ_{0i} and $\epsilon_{\infty i}$ are static dielectric constant and dielectric constant at high

frequency respectively and g_i is the correlation factor. In general, the static dielectric permittivity of a mixture of different dipolar species is not just given by the amount of the molecular dipole moments and the concentrations of the dipolar species, but also by the dipole orientation correlation factor⁷ and by a permittivity ϵ_∞ . Water-glycerol dipole orientation correlations have to be considered in the static permittivity of the mixtures. Since we can not derive two correlation factors from the single permittivity value, we extend the model by introducing an effective dipole orientation correlation factor g^{eff} as follows¹⁰:

$$\frac{4\pi N}{9kT} \left[\frac{\mu_g^2 \rho_g (1-V)}{M_g} + \frac{\mu_w^2 \rho_w V}{M_w} \right] g^{\text{eff}} = \frac{(\epsilon_{0m} - \epsilon_{\infty m})(2\epsilon_{0m} + \epsilon_{\infty m})}{\epsilon_{0m}(\epsilon_{\infty m} + 2)^2} \quad (3)$$

where, μ_g and μ_w are the dipole moments of glycerol and water, ρ_g and ρ_w are corresponding densities. V is the volume fraction of water and m indicates the binary mixture. To calculate g^{eff} values, we have taken dipole moment of glycerol and water as 2.67 D and 1.84 D respectively. The high values of g^{eff} indicate parallel orientation of electric dipoles in molecule⁷. As water is added in glycerol at regular steps in the mixture, it can be seen from Fig. 3 that the values of g^{eff} increases. The increase of correlation in glycerol and glycerol-water mixtures may be due to association effect.

The contribution of hydrogen bonds to dielectric properties of mixture can be studied by using the hydrogen bonded model as suggested by Luzar¹². The value of g cannot be calculated directly for mixtures. The theory of H-bonded liquids can be simplified because the effect of the second next neighbour can be neglected and by assuming that only certain specific angles between dipoles neighbouring molecules are possible. Hence Luzar¹² had suggested model for calculation of Kirkwood correlation factors g_1 and g_2 for two components in the mixture theoretically. This model is based on Kirkwood-Frohlich equation for a mixture of polarizable molecule is in the form

$$g_1 = 1 + \sum_{i=1}^2 Z_{1i} \overline{\cos \phi_{1i}} \mu_i / \mu_1 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{where } Z_{11} = 2 \langle n_{\text{HB}}^{11} \rangle$$

$$Z_{12} = 2 \langle n_{\text{HB}}^{12} \rangle$$

$$g_2 = 1 + Z_{21} \overline{\cos \phi_{21}} \mu_1 / \mu_2$$

$$Z_{21} = \langle n_{\text{HB}}^{12} \rangle X / (1 - X)$$

where only the nearest Z_{ij} neighbours of species j forming the hydrogen bond with central i , taken into consideration. The average value $\overline{\cos \phi_{ij}}$ is taken as 1/3 by assuming tetrahedral coordination of water free rotation of OH-O bond. The values of g^{eff} , g_1 and g_2 for triol-water mixture is shown in Fig. 3.

Fig. 3a. g^{eff} values for glycerol-water mixtures at different temperatures.

Fig. 3b. g_1 values for glycerol-water mixtures at different temperatures.

Fig. 3c. g_2 values for glycerol-water mixtures at different temperatures.

Using the Luzar model theoretical values of static permittivity (ϵ_0) are calculated. It can be seen from Table 2 that the experimental data can be explained by the theory provided values of dipole moment for water and glycerol is taken as 1.85 D and 2.67 D, respectively in gas phase. The Luzar model gives good qualitative account of the dielectric constant for triol-water mixture. The different parameters used to calculate the theoretical values are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Molecular parameters used in computation of the static dielectric constant

Molecular parameters	Water	Glycerol
Dipole moment (μ_1, μ_2)	1.85 D	2.67 D
Polarizability (α_1, α_2)	1.78 \AA^3	13.56 \AA^3
Bonding energy (E_{11}, E_{12})	-13.39 kJ/mol	-18.25 kJ/mol

E_{11} , water-water pair; E_{12} , water-glycerol pair.

Table 2. Theoretical values of the static dielectric constants as calculated by the model suggested by Luzar along with experimental values for glycerol-water mixtures

Volume fraction of	15 °C		25 °C		35 °C	
	Expt. ^a	Theo. ^b	Expt. ^a	Theo. ^b	Expt. ^a	Theo. ^b
water						
0.00	43.23	43.79	41.40	41.83	39.57	39.58
0.10	48.68	44.49	48.55	45.17	46.34	51.07
0.20	54.60	51.93	52.38	52.98	50.46	59.40
0.30	58.16	58.24	56.27	58.86	54.55	64.44
0.40	62.22	63.25	59.82	63.79	57.37	68.73
0.50	65.24	67.28	63.55	67.73	58.88	71.92
0.60	69.64	70.55	66.91	70.90	64.63	72.27
0.70	72.11	73.20	70.84	73.45	67.85	72.98
0.80	74.13	75.36	73.89	75.51	70.50	73.20
0.90	74.69	77.12	70.30	77.17	70.57	74.01
1.00	82.18	81.54	78.55	78.50	74.50	75.23

^aExperimental values determined from TDR. ^bCalculated by the model suggested by Luzar¹².

The Luzar model is also capable of describing strong orientation dependent attractive interactions e.g. hydrogen bonds. The method involves simpler functions namely average number of hydrogen bonds made by water-water and water-glycerol pairs. The average number of hydrogen bonds water molecules for $1i$ pairs ($i = 1, 2$) have been determined by using following relationship

$$\langle n_{HB}^{1i} \rangle = n_{1i} \omega_{1i} / n_1$$

where, n_1 is number of density pairs of water molecules, represents water-water pair for $i = 1$ and water-glycerol pair for $i = 2$. The term is probability of bond formation. These two quantities, calculated and are shown in Fig. 4 as functions of the volume fraction of water. It can be conclude from the Fig. 4 that the foreign component i.e. added solute in solvent locally modify the surrounded by glycerol molecules and forms hydrogen bonds with it. Hence accordingly $\langle n_{HB}^{12} \rangle$ decreases and $\langle n_{HB}^{11} \rangle$ increases with volume fraction of water. In higher water concentration, water molecule may form hydrogen bonding with water as well as with glycerol molecules. The $\langle n_{HB}^{11} \rangle$ and $\langle n_{HB}^{12} \rangle$ depend on number of density pairs between both the species in the mixture.

The Bruggeman factor :

In order to understand the dipole-dipole interaction on the mixture of two liquids, various mixtures formulae have been proposed⁷. The Bruggeman equation for binary mixture is given by expression^{13,14},

$$f_B = \left(\frac{\epsilon_{0m} - \epsilon_{02}}{\epsilon_{01} - \epsilon_{02}} \right) \left(\frac{\epsilon_{01}}{\epsilon_{0m}} \right)^{1/3} = 1 - V \quad (5)$$

where, f_B is the Bruggeman dielectric factor, ϵ_{0m} , ϵ_{01} and ϵ_{02} are the static dielectric constant corresponding to mixture, glycerol and water respectively. V is the volume fraction of water. It can be seen that the Bruggeman factor

Fig. 4. Plot of average number of hydrogen bonds between water-water molecule (n_{11} pair) and water-glycerol (n_{12} pair) against volume fraction of water at 25 °C temperature.

is a linear function of the volume fraction as predicted by the Bruggeman equation. The experimental values show non-linear relationship. Therefore, the modified Bruggeman equation is fitted by assuming non-linear behavior as¹⁴

$$f_B = \left(\frac{\epsilon_{0m} - \epsilon_{02}}{\epsilon_{01} - \epsilon_{02}} \right) \left(\frac{\epsilon_{01}}{\epsilon_{0m}} \right)^{1/3} = 1 - [a - (a-1)V]V \quad (6)$$

In this equation, it is assumed that the volume fraction (V) of solvent in the mixture is modified by a factor of $[a - (a-1)V]$. This modification in volume fraction may be due to the structural rearrangement of solvent molecules in the mixture. The value of a contains the information regarding the change in the orientation of solvent molecule in the mixture. The value of a is determined by the least squares fit method. The values are given in Table 3 at different temperatures. The experimental and theoretical values of Bruggeman dielectric (f_B) versus volume fraction of water in glycerol is shown in Fig. 5.

The excess dielectric constant :

The excess dielectric constant parameters approach is useful which may provide some trend regarding the interactions in the binary liquids. The contribution of hydrogen bonds to the dielectric properties of mixtures is studied in terms of the excess static dielectric constant. The excess permittivity (ϵ_0^E) may also provide structural information. This is determined for the glycerol-water solutions as follows⁷,

$$\epsilon_0^E = (\epsilon_0)_M - [(\epsilon_0)_W X_1 + (\epsilon_0)_A(1 - X_1)] \quad (7)$$

where $(\epsilon_0)_M$, $(\epsilon_0)_W$ and $(\epsilon_0)_A$ represent values static dielectric constant corresponding to mixture, water and glycerol, respectively and X_1 is the volume fraction of water.

Fig. 5. Bruggeman dielectric factor (f_B) against volume fraction of water (V). Solid line represents theoretical curve according to Bruggeman model (eq. (5)). Symbol (■) denote the experimental values of triol-water mixtures. Symbol (◆) represents theoretical curve obtained from (eq. (6)).

Table 3. Bruggeman factor for glycerol-water mixtures

Temperature (°C)	a values
15	1.76
25	1.60
35	1.43

Fig. 6. Excess permittivity vs volume fraction of water.

The excess permittivity (ϵ_0^E) may provide qualitative information in the mixture as follows :

(i) $\epsilon_0^E = 0$ indicates that water and alcohol do not interact at all.

(ii) $\epsilon_0^E < 0$ indicates that water and alcohol interaction is such that the total effective dipolar polarization get reduced.

Water and alcohol may form multimers leading to the less effective dipoles.

The resulting excess dielectric constants of water-glycerol mixture are shown in Fig. 6. The negative values of excess permittivity were observed. The negative values of excess parameter suggest that the addition of glycerol to water may create multimeric structure leading to decrease in the total permittivity. The hydrogen bonded model gives quantitative agreement with the experimental data of excess dielectric constant of the mixture.

Conclusion :

In this work, the systematic study of complex permittivity of glycerol-water mixtures have been carried out from 10 MHz to 20 GHz at different temperatures. The Kirkwood correlation factor g^{eff} at different temperatures and concentrations are also determined to explain association effect in water-glycerol mixtures. The correlation factor g_1 and g_2 are also determined by employing hydrogen bonded model. The experimental static dielectric constant is compared with theoretical values. A modification in Bruggeman-model provides better description of dielectric behaviour in mixtures.

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